

1 **SUPPLEMENTARY FILES**

2 **Table S1:** Collection of isolates used in this study.

3 **Table S2:** Synonymous polymorphisms detected in the cyp51B gene of the isolates ATCC46645, PD-9,
4 PD-60 and PD-104.

5 **Table S3:** GO enrichment of genes regulated exclusively in Persistence (A1163 genome as reference).

6 **Table S4:** GO enrichment of genes regulated in Persiter VS Low Drug (Pangenome as reference).

7 **Table S5:** GO enrichment of genes regulated exclusively in Persistence (Pangenome as reference).

8 **Table S6:** Proteins included in the STRING network (genes upregulated only in Persistence).

9 **Table S7:** GO enrichment of genes regulated more in Persistence (Pangenome as reference).

10 **Table S8:** Proteins included in the STRING network (genes upregulated more in Persistence).

11 **Table S9:** List of environmental isolates in the UK collection. Identity of the sequenced genomes. List
12 of the clinical isolates of the TAU collection.

13 **Table S10:** Primers utilized to analyse the relative expression of selected genes by RT-PCR.

14 **Table S11:** Example of the Quast obtained to determine the quality of the assembly, using the PD- 104
15 genome.

16 **DataSet1:** RNA-seq results and analysis of the A1160 isolate grown in NoDrug and Low Drug.

17 **DataSet2:** RNA-seq results and analysis of the PD-104 isolate grown in NoDrug, Low Drug and
18 Persister, using the A1163 genome as reference for the alignment of reads.

19 **DataSet3:** RNA-seq results and analysis of the PD-104 isolate grown in NoDrug, Low Drug and
20 Persister, using the pangenome genome as reference for the alignment of reads.

21 **Video S1:** The persister isolate PD-9 pre-incubated in voriconazole resumes growth when the drug is
22 withdrawn.

23 **Video S2:** The persister isolate PD-104 pre-incubated in voriconazole resumes growth when the drug
24 is withdrawn.

25 **Video S3:** The non-persister isolate ATCC46645 pre-incubated in voriconazole resumes growth when
26 the drug is withdrawn

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